

REGULATORY FRAMEWORK OF CORPORATE FINANCIAL REPORTING PRACTICES IN INDIA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COMPANIES ACT 2013

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ABSTRACT

Under the Companies act 1956, there was no regulatory framework for preparing financial statements of business to the different users. The business enterprises were regulated as per their own self-made regulations. Companies' Act 2013 and IND AS have brought in a clear cut format of reporting financial information to meet the requirements of globalised business enterprises. In our study we have shown the impact of Companies act 2013 on firm's performance. Paired t test has been used to find out the impact. The study found there is no significant impact of Companies Act 2013 on firm's performance.

Keywords: *Companies Act, IND AS, Globalised business.*

Introduction:

Accounting is a language of business. It is a system of recording business information and communicating the information to shareholders which helps for financial decision making. But there was no formal standard for financial reporting.

The new companies' act 2013 has a major influence in reshaping Indian financial reporting. It comprises 470 sections, 7 schedules and 29 chapters. Under new companies Act many new provisions are incorporated under financial reporting like uniform financial year, National financial reporting authority, board report etc.

Review of Literature:

Bhattacharjee (1995) examined the relevance and use of published corporate accounting information for the investors. The findings of the study revealed that there exists a wide gap between the disclosure of information in the annual reports of the companies and the information needs of the individual investors. He suggested that the company management must emphasize on incorporation of statutory and non-statutory information in the corporate annual reports in a manner that was adequate both substance wise and format wise.

Chakraborti (1990) analyzed the annual reports of 50 companies for 1980 and 1985 to find out the recent developments in corporate financial reporting in India. Findings of study showed that the annual reports disclosed more statutory information than the non-statutory information. He suggested that the disclosure of significant accounting policies used in the preparation of financial statements should be made obligatory to enhance the reliability and credibility of the annual reports.

Chander (1992) made a comparative analysis of disclosure practices of public and private sector companies in India during 1980-81 to 1984-85. His Findings showed that item wise disclosure and company wise disclosure was significantly better in public sector companies as compared to private sector companies and considerable improvements were seen in the disclosure practices of public and private sector companies over the period of analysis.

Gupta (1977) studied the financial reporting practices of India, Australia, USA and UK etc. He concluded that present reports were insufficient for modern business conditions and did not disclose the necessary information required in these days of complex trading conditions. He suggested that the statement of highlights, summarized balance sheet and profit and loss account, narrating statements, statistical records,

and diagrams and charts etc. should be included in the annual reports of the companies.

Kohli (1998) made a comprehensive attempt to compare the current status of disclosure level of Indian and U.S. companies for the years 1990-91 to 1994-95. He found that there was improvement in mean disclosure score of Indian companies over the period of study. He suggested that in order to make the corporate annual reports more informative and decision oriented, these must provide detailed information about their future plans and policies.

Lal (1985) analyzed the financial reporting practices of 180 private sector manufacturing companies from 1965 to 1975. He found that the quality of disclosure improved considerably during the period under study. There was positive association between the size of the company, earnings margin, nature of industry and the association with a large industrial house with the extent of disclosure.

Rathod (1990) examined the recent trends in financial reporting in corporate sector in India. He found the companies which were presenting their annual reports in magazine size keeping the front cover blank except for putting down the name of the company and the year to which it pertains. He concluded that the financial reporting of corporate sector had got immense value in the present day context.

Statement of Problem:

“Does financial reporting practices by corporate affect the financial decisions made by stakeholders. Is it required?”

Objectives:

1. To evaluate the impact of companies act 2013 on the performance measurement of Tata Motors a manufacturing company.
2. To examine the impact of companies Act, 2013 on the performance measurement of Tata Consultancy a Service sector company.

Hypothesis:

H₀: Changes in regulatory framework from Company's act 1956 to Company's act 2013 have no significant impact on measurement of financial performance of the company.

Research Methodology:

Sources of Data:

For the study secondary data have been taken. The required data are collected from company's annual report and Money control website.

Sample Design:

The study consists of top manufacturing company and top service Sector Company on the basis of market capitalization. We have taken Tata Consultancy

Services for service sector and Tata Motors for manufacturing sector. We have selected 12 key indicators for measuring performance of the company. Because of non-availability of some indicators from the financial statement of the sample companies, five indicators such as current ratio, Debt equity ratio, Asset turnover ratio, Inventory turnover ratio and Return on Equity have been considered for our study.

Tools:

We have used Paired sample T test for analysis of our data.

Key Indicators:

- Current Ratio
- Debt Equity ratio
- Asset Turnover ratio
- Inventory turnover Ratio
- Return on Equity

Data Analysis:

After collection of data it is necessary to analyze and interpret data for final result and findings. In this study researcher has used CR, DER, ATR, ITR and ROE to find out the impact of Companies act 2013 on financial performance. All the calculations are carried out by using SPSS V20 software and Microsoft excel 2007.

TCS:

Table no 1 shows paired sample test of Current ratio before companies act 1956 and after Companies act 2013. The P value is 0.052 which is above than standard i.e. 0.05. Hence H₀ is accepted. It indicates that there is no significant difference between current ratio before companies act 1956 and current ratio after company's act 2013. Whatever difference exist it is because of sampling fluctuation. In other words company's act 2013 has not changed a much with respect to current ratio as compared to Company's act 1956.

The above table describes about Debt Equity ratio before companies act 1956 and after company's act 2013. Here P value is 1 which is above than standard i.e. 0.05. So, null hypothesis is accepted. It means that there is no significant difference between debt equity ratio before companies act 1956 and debt equity ratio after company's act 2013. If any difference is there it is because of sampling fluctuation. In other words company's act 2013 has not changed a much with respect to debt equity ratio as compared to Company's act 1956.

Accordingly to the table Paired samples test of asset turnover shows P value is 0.839 which is above than standard i.e. 0.05. Hence null hypothesis is accepted. It states that there is no significant difference between asset turnover ratio before companies act 1956 and asset turnover ratio after company's act 2013. Especially company's act 2013 has not changed a

much with respect to asset turnover ratio as compared to Company's act 1956.

We can find out the above table displays paired sample test of Inventory turnover ratio before company's act 1956 and after Company's act 2013. Here the P value is 0.924 which is above than standard i.e. 0.05. Hence H_0 is accepted. It indicates that there is no significant difference between inventory turnover ratio before Companies act 1956 and inventory turnover ratio after company's act 2013. If there is any difference exist it is because of sampling fluctuation. In other words company's act 2013 has not changed a much with respect to inventory turnover ratio as compared to Company's act 1956.

The paired sample test between ROE before companies act 1956 and after company's act 2013 shows the P value i.e. 0.901 which is more than standard i.e. 0.05. Hence null hypothesis is accepted. It indicates that there is no significant difference between return on equity before companies act 1956 and return on equity after company's act 2013. Whatever difference exist it is because of sampling fluctuation. Especially company's act 2013 has not changed a much with respect to ROE as compared to Company's act 1956.

TATA Motors:

Table no 2 shows paired sample test of Current ratio before companies act 1956 and after Company's act 2013. Here the P value is 0.460 which is above than standard i.e. 0.05. Hence H_0 is accepted. It states that there is no significant difference between current ratio before companies act 1956 and current ratio after company's act 2013. If any difference exists it is because of sampling error. In other words company's act 2013 has not changed a much with respect to current ratio as compared to Company's act 1956.

The above table shows paired sample test of Debt Equity ratio before companies act 1956 and after company's act 2013. The P value is 0.495 which is more than standard i.e. 0.05. Hence null hypothesis is accepted. It indicates that there is no significant difference between debt equity ratio before companies act 1956 and debt equity ratio after company's act 2013. Whatever difference exist it is because of sampling fluctuation. Especially company's act 2013 has not changed a much with respect to ROE as compared to Company's act 1956.

The P value of paired t test is 0.121 which is above than standard i.e. 0.05. Hence H_0 is accepted. It states that there is no significant difference between asset turnover ratio before companies act 1956 and asset turnover ratio after company's act 2013. If any difference exists it is because of sampling error. In other words company's act 2013 has not changed a much with respect to asset turnover ratio as compared to Company's act 1956.

In the above table we can find paired sample test of inventory turnover ratio before companies act 1956 and

after company's act 2013. Here P value is 0.071 which is more than standard i.e. 0.05. Hence null hypothesis is accepted. It means that there is no significant difference between inventory turnover ratio before Companies act 1956 and inventory turnover ratio after company's act 2013. Whatever difference exist it is because of sampling fluctuation. In other words company's act 2013 has not changed a much with respect to ROE as compared to Company's act 1956.

The paired sample test of ROE before company's act 1956 and after Company's act 2013 shows the P value i.e. 0.317 which is above than standard i.e. 0.05. So H_0 is accepted. It means that there is no significant difference between return on equity before companies act 1956 and return on equity after company's act 2013. If any difference is there it is because of sampling error. In other words company's act 2013 has not changed a much with respect to return on equity as compared to Company's act 1956.

Findings:

There is no significant impact of Company's act 2013 on measurement of financial performance of the company.

Conclusion:

With the growth and expansion of business, it was difficult to meet the requirements of competitive business world without any regulatory framework. So always there was a challenge for business enterprises to satisfy the needs of different stakeholders of the business. Companies' Act 1956 though had some provisions for recording and communicating financial information but there was no prescribed format of reporting financial statements. As time passes many amendments have been made in companies' Act 1956, accounting standards and many other regulatory bodies to provide as much financial information as required by the stakeholders. With the advent of Liberalization, Privatization and Globalisation a lot of emphasis is being given to social and environmental issues resulted from competitive business across the globe. Since then the corporate financial reporting practices have undergone a sea change. India is not exception to it. Company's' Act 2013 and IND AS have brought in a clear cut format of reporting financial information to meet the requirements of globalised business enterprises. In our study we have outlined the impact of Companies act 2013 on financial performance. It is expected that this would help all the stakeholders in making their respective financial decisions more effectively and efficiently than before. Change in companies act from 1956 to 2013 does not have much impact on financial performance of the company, however if number of year data taken is increased the result might be different. In the present business environment triple

bottom lines such as profit, planet and people reporting should be made mandatory.

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Table no 1: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	d.f	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Current Ratio 1956 - 2013	-.76333	.30892	.17836	-1.53074	.00407	-4.280	2	.052
Debt Equity Ratio 1956 - 2013	.00000	.01000	.00577	-.02484	.02484	.000	2	1.000
Asset Turnover 1956 -2013	-.35667	2.66988	1.54145	-6.98900	6.27567	-.231	2	.839
Inventory Turnover 1956 - 2013	-194.69	3134.807	1809.882	-7981.98400	7592.60400	-.108	2	.924
ROE 1956 - 2013	-2.1000	2.57659	1.48759	-6.61060	6.19060	-.141	2	.901

Source: Self Compiled

Table 2: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	d.f	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Current Ratio 1956 - 2013	.10000	.19079	.11015	-.37394	.57394	.908	2	.460
Debt Equity Ratio 1956 - 2013	-.23333	.48789	.28168	-1.44531	.97864	-.828	2	.495
Asset Turnover 1956 -2013	16.61667	11.04055	6.37426	-10.80958	44.04291	2.607	2	.121
Inventory Turnover 1956 - 2013	2.97000	1.45124	.83787	-.63508	6.57508	3.545	2	.071
ROE 1956 - 2013	15.37000	20.11194	11.61163	-34.59083	65.33083	1.324	2	.317

Source: Self Compiled
